

REFLECTIONS ON TRANSLATION AND PLURILINGUAL STRATEGIES: ITALIAN AND ITALIANS IN MALTESE SCHOOLS

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"Conceived as linguistically and culturally homogenous spaces, our schools find it difficult to question their monolingual habitus, and to imagine that multilingual practices could become the norm in education as well" (Helot, 2012:215). Teaching foreign languages in many European schools, including those in Malta, is often characterised by approaches in which focus is placed on the target language (TL), without necessarily giving space to strategies through which the L1 and/or previously known languages can also support learning TLs. Such strategies may also include the use of indirect translation when, in the Maltese educational context, shifts occur from Maltese to English (or vice versa) to teach Italian.

Italian is generally learnt (chronologically) as a third language (L3) at the start of secondary schooling: Maltese nationals are bilingual (Maltese & English) and migrant learners normally possess competences in their L1 and in a foreign language, often English. In the contribution I reflect on how students' linguistic background can be better exploited when teachers use strategies based on their own plurilingualism, which can also enable them to resort to indirect translation. Examples will be taken both from Italian classes in Malta and from reflections of Italian students in Maltese schools, and their use of English terminology. These reflections also coincide with perspectives put forward through the Dynamic Model of Multilingualism (Herdina & Jessner, 2002) which "rejects the notion of individual 'language' in a traditional sense, emphasising the existence of 'individual language systems' that are themselves part of a larger psycholinguistic system" (Rothman et al. 2019:59). I claim that making teachers more aware of plurilingual strategies, including indirect translation, may be conducive to L3 teaching and learning.

References:

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